

Guidance Document for Health Assessments

INFORMATION

Health risks of excessive energy shot intake

BfR Opinion No. 01/2010, 2 December 2009

So-called energy shots are a new kind of energy drink that contain caffeine and taurine. In advertisements, these are claimed to increase concentration and capacity or physical performance. They are marketed in smaller portions (25-75 ml) than the more common energy drinks yet contain a higher concentration of caffeine and in some cases taurine per litre than energy drinks. The composition of energy shots known to BfR vary significantly and contains between 50-200 mg caffeine and 200-1000 mg taurine per portion. In contrast to energy drinks, these energy shots are labelled with the manufacturer's suggested intake level. All of those known to BfR thus far uniformly recommend one portion per day.

In BfR's opinion, energy shots that contain the constituents listed above pose no health risk if consumed in accordance with the manufacturer's intended use, i.e. one portion per day, and other product labels.

Health risks can result if the suggested intake level is exceeded considerably. This could mean that the constituents (caffeine and taurine) are consumed in considerably higher amounts and/or over a shorter time span than before with ordinary energy drinks. Yet the potential risk should be estimated differently due to varying amounts of caffeine and taurine in individual energy shots. Excessive doses of caffeine can lead to risks associated with known potential adverse effects. Excessive doses of caffeine can lead to risks associated with known potential adverse effects. It remains to be clarified whether the interaction of caffeine with other constituents in energy drinks (e.g. taurine) or with ethanol in the alcoholic beverages consumed alongside energy shots or with physical exertion (e.g. endurance, physically strenuous training or sports activities) could amplify the adverse effects of caffeine. An actual causal relationship between these factors has not yet been scientifically demonstrated. The extent of potential health risks depends on the intake amounts (caffeine and taurine) and the manner of intake (e.g. once, rapid intake over a short period of time, high amounts distributed over several single doses), on individual consumer sensitivity to the effects of caffeine, the usual amount of caffeine consumed daily, the amount of caffeine consumed through other sources of caffeine as well as potential parallel factors such as alcohol intake or strenuous physical sports activity.

According to BfR, there is a risk that energy shots are not used in accordance with the manufacturer's advice for intended use. This includes assuming that energy shots are sometimes consumed in place of energy drinks and thus consumed – like these – at the discretion of the consumer without quantitative limits. It should also be noted that consumers in tight clubs may choose to increase their energy shot intake in an attempt to counteract fatigue or to reach a state of arousal. Since physical exertion also increases thirst, there is a risk that the suggested intake levels of energy shots are not adhered to.

According to BfR, the danger is

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energy drinks are non-alcoholic beverages that contain high amounts of caffeine and taurine and sometimes glucuronolactone and inositol. However, the concentration of caffeine and taurine in energy shots far exceeds the amounts allowed in energy drinks. The Federal Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Consumer Protection (BMELV) has asked the Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) to issue an opinion on the consumer health risk of these products.

At the time of the assessment, seven energy shots are known to BfR. Five of these products are labelled as dietary supplements. One product is labelled a dietary supplement for intense muscular exertion, especially for athletes. One other product is also intended for athletes.

The caffeine concentration in these products is 1.3-6 g/L, the taurine concentration is 4-20 g/L, and portion volumes are 25-75 ml. Present information indicates that all products carry the manufacturer's advice for intended use, which uniformly state one portion per day. If used accordingly, caffeine intake is 50-200 mg/day and taurine intake is 200-1000 mg/day depending on each product. In six of the products, the caffeine concentration is provided exclusively by caffeine. In one product it is provided exclusively by guarana extract. Some of the products contain added inositol (up to 50 mg/portion) and few products have added glucuronolactone (7 mg/portion), while one product contains no information on the amounts added.

Upon the accession of one product, the labels indicate increased caffeine concentration and one product (200 mg caffeine/portion) carries the notice "high caffeine concentration". Five products also carry warning labels stating that they are not suitable for children, pregnant women and caffeine-sensitive individuals, and in some cases additional groups (e.g. breastfeeding mothers, diabetics) are named. One product (200 mg caffeine/portion) is labelled unsuitable for individuals with high blood pressure and cardiovascular disease in addition to children and pregnant and breast-feeding women.

2 Results

The composition of energy shots assessed here vary significantly (caffeine concentrations 1.3-6 g/L, taurine concentrations 4-20 g/L). With respect to the manufacturer's advice for intended use (1 portion/day), caffeine intake ranges from 50-200 mg and taurine intake ranges from 200-1000 mg/day.

Consumer health can be at risk if the intake of the energy shots is question considerably exceeds the amount indicated on the label. In this case, the constituents (caffeine and taurine) may have been consumed in considerably higher amounts and/or over shorter periods of time than intended. This could amplify the adverse effects of caffeine. Furthermore, it is suspected that consumers in tight clubs may choose to increase their energy shot intake in an attempt to counteract fatigue or to reach a state of arousal. Since physical exertion also increases thirst, there is a risk that the suggested intake levels of energy shots are not adhered to.

2010

Risiken erkennen – Gesundheit schützen

Imprint

Guidance Document for Health Assessments

Publisher: BfR, Unit Clearing, EFSA Focal Point and Committees

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The Guidance Document for Health Assessments is available online (www.bfr.bund.de) and in print.

ISBN 3-938163-72-0

ISSN 1614-5070 (Print)

ISSN 1614-5089 (Online)

Guidance Document for Health Assessments

2010 Edition

Federal Institute for Risk Assessment

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I Principles

1 Aim of the guidance document

- (1) The Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) is responsible for evaluating, assessing and, if necessary and possible, recommending measures for minimising and avoiding **risks for human health of substances, microorganisms, products and processes** and to provide possible options for action. In some instances it is also necessary to assess the benefit of substances, products or processes that is claimed (e.g. “health claims”, efficacy of biocides).
- (2) The Opinions especially serve as **scientific basis** for:
 - ▶ Decisions regarding the authorisation of products based on the product dossier and BfR’s own information,
 - ▶ Decisions regarding action of those **authorities** that control food, chemical or product legislation,
 - ▶ **Court** decisions regarding food, chemical or product safety and
 - ▶ Actions by the national or EU **legislative body** or other political authority.
- (3) BfR statements are to be in line with internationally recognised principles and are to include **reasoning that is transparent** for third parties. This is to incorporate and depict existing knowledge adequately and clearly. Relevant opposing scientific positions are to be included as well. References to previous BfR statements pertinent to the issue should be established.
- (4) It may be the case that the **data** used to draw up an Opinion is scientifically insufficient. Yet even in cases where the state of scientific knowledge is incomplete, measures regarding consumer health protection are often valid or even mandatory. This must be taken into account when risk assessments are drawn up because they are meant to serve as a basis for decisions.
- (5) Wherever it is possible and appropriate, BfR incorporates **external expert knowledge** in the process of drawing up an Opinion, e.g. by consulting with BfR Committees.
- (6) BfR is required to **publicly communicate** assessments that are of public interest, as long as confidentiality issues are not compromised.
- (7) **This “Guidance Document for Health Assessments” serves to implement the above stated principles into practice in order to assure the quality of BfR assessments.** Members of BfR staff are instructed to use the guidance document as a standard for scientific Opinions published by BfR as far as possible.
- (8) The guidance document constitutes a standard for the depiction of BfR health assessments, yet it is to be utilised flexibly. Deviations are possible, especially in cases where legal requirements apply or other forms of expression are more suited to a subject-specific issue. The legal scope of the guidance document is explained in Chapter III, p. 19 et seqq.

- (9) The guidance document is reviewed and edited on a regular basis.

2 Fundamentals of BfR health assessments

- (10) A **risk assessment** is the analysis of a risk by means of scientific methods. This includes:

- ▶ **Identification of a possible risk source** (“hazard identification”), i.e. the biological, chemical or physical agent which could have adverse health effects must be identified;
- ▶ **Characterisation of the hazard potential** (“hazard characterisation”), i.e. the qualitative and/or quantitative evaluation of adverse health effects that could arise from the risk source, if necessary under consideration of a dose-response relationship;
- ▶ Depending on the request, an **assessment of human exposure** (“exposure assessment”), i.e. the qualitative and/or quantitative evaluation of the intake of an agent with regard to the relevant routes of exposure in individual cases (intake through food intake, breathing or skin contact);
- ▶ Finally, a **characterisation of the actual risk** (“risk characterisation”), i.e. the qualitative and/or quantitative evaluation of the frequency and severity of adverse health effects in a certain segment of the population under consideration of uncertainties related to the assessment.

- (11) In **qualitative risk assessments**, risks are described verbally. The description follows the structure outlined in (10) as conceptual model. In contrast, **quantitative risk assessments** are at least partially based on calculations or mathematical models, and risks are

described in mathematical or statistical terms based on these methods. In case a mathematical model is used, this should be selected for the specific risk question and depicted in a transparent manner. The numerical results of the model should be described verbally and incorporated in the answer to the request.

- (12) The following **criteria** are a selection of those to be taken into account for the risk assessment:
- ▶ The **affected population** or segment of the population (e.g. pregnant women, the elderly, sick people, children);
 - ▶ The **probability** and, if it applies, the frequency of an adverse effect;
 - ▶ The **nature and severity** of a possible adverse effect;
 - ▶ The **reversibility** of a possible adverse effect;
 - ▶ The **empirical evidence** for a causal relationship and **weight of evidence**;
 - ▶ The **nature and quality** of available data including variability and uncertainty;
 - ▶ The **controllability** of the risk. Whether or not consumers are able to minimise the risk is taken into account, e.g. heeding product information.
- (13) **Transparency** is essential on all levels of the risk assessment process. The assessment is to be comprehensible and reproducible from the initial objective to the scope of an opinion as well as source, nature and evidence of the underlying data, the methods, assumptions, uncertainty and variability all the way to the result and conclusion.
- (14) BfR **risk assessments** are also subject to the Institute’s risk communication as **risk communication** refers to the

purpose-specific exchange of risk information and opinions between stakeholders. Stakeholders include members of politics, science, public bodies, associations, non-governmental organisations and the mass media as well as individual citizens. Risk communication with all stakeholders – including knowledgeable target audiences – should follow the key basic rules of transparent, comprehensible and useful risk communication.

- (15) If there are different scientific views on a point critical to the result of an Opinion, these are to be indicated transparently. If such a **divergence of opinions** of different national authorities or EU authorities exists, these differences are to be depicted especially precisely. Other scientists are then able to form their own opinion on the issue based on the explication.

3 Language use and terminology

- (16) BfR Opinions are to use **recipient-specific** wording and reflect the current state of science with transparent reasoning. The Opinions are especially addressed to national and Länder authorities, which base their statutory authorisation and other executive decisions on BfR Opinions, as well as Federal Ministries that require basic scientific information for their political work. It is to be expected that recipients of BfR Opinions will pass these on to third parties.
- (17) BfR Opinions should use **target group-specific** wording as much as possible. The target audience is broader than the original group of recipients. The target audience in particular includes members of politics, industry and consumer as-

sociations as well as individual citizens, e.g. applicants for national authorisation procedures. The Opinions can be used in scientific debates as well as in a judicial or political setting. Statements are to be well suited for use by the recipients and target groups without the need for further explanation. They are therefore to be worded in generally understandable terms, i.e. in lay terms.

- (18) The wording is to be **unambiguous and coherent** within the context of other BfR Opinions.
- (19) As far as possible, the assessment terminology used should be **harmonised**, e.g. in regard to assessment criteria, preferably based on an internationally recognised nomenclature. Terms should be consistent, clear and appropriate.
- (20) In order to avoid linguistic diversity which could lead to misunderstandings, **synonyms** should be avoided, especially for the characterisation of health risks.
- (21) **Abbreviations and technical terms** should be written out completely when first introduced and explained in generally understandable terms.
- (22) BfR Opinions are to include enough information necessary for understanding, but not more. Unnecessary **reiteration** is to be avoided. When an Opinion is published, an abstract is added.

- (23) If information regarding risk is communicated, the reference should be explained as clearly as possible and varied as rarely as possible within one text or section of a text. Examples: “not more than 100g per day”; “carcinogenic in animal tests”; “carcinogenic for humans”. It should also be noted that concentration data and units of measure are used consistently throughout the entire text in order to ensure **comparability** of data for laypersons as well (e.g. mg/kg body weight).
- (24) Primarily **numerical descriptions** are to be used as far as they are available in regard to the frequency of adverse events, the extent of an adverse health effect, the probability of an occurrence of a risk etc. Thus, instead of a descriptive specification (e.g. an adverse event occurs “often”) numerical descriptions should be used (e.g. “the event occurred in x out of y cases”; or “no cases are known to have occurred”). The phrase “health risks cannot be excluded” should be avoided as especially in a court of law it has no merit. Numerical descriptions in the form of absolute frequencies (10 out of 1000 cases) are more easily understood by the target audience than percentages, especially if the percentages are small with decimal places.
- (25) The **frequency of adverse events** can be indicated with keywords such as:
- ▶ Often,
 - ▶ Occasionally,
 - ▶ Rarely,
 - ▶ Unknown to have occurred.
- (26) The **severity of an adverse health effect** may be indicated with keywords such as:
- ▶ Serious,
 - ▶ Moderate,
 - ▶ Slight,
 - ▶ Mild.
- In addition, whether the adverse effect is chronic or acute, reversible or irreversible is taken into account.
- (27) The **probability of the occurrence** of an event is characterised as:
- ▶ Certain,
 - ▶ Probable,
 - ▶ Possible,
 - ▶ Improbable,
 - ▶ Practically impossible.
- Reference values for the interpretation of the terms (e.g. “certain: in more than 99 out of 100 cases” or by a comparison with known probabilities) should be provided. If quantitative assessments are available, these should be provided.
- (28) **Evidence of a causal relationship** between possible risk source and the adverse health effect is characterised as:
- ▶ Generally accepted proof (= causality has been verified and accepted by the scientific community),
 - ▶ Fact-supported reasons to suspect this (= facts make causality plausible),
 - ▶ A concern (= relatively vague indications of a risk),
 - ▶ No indications of risk.

It should be noted that statistical significance is not to be equated with biological significance. A statistically “significant” risk factor can be biologically irrelevant.

- (29) The **origin of data** upon which the risk assessment is based must be indicated.

This can include:

- ▶ The authorisation dossier of a company according to a legal provision,
- ▶ Scientific publications,
- ▶ Other publically accessible information,
- ▶ Opinions of scientific committees or experts,
- ▶ Results from monitoring programmes, data from food consumption surveys,
- ▶ Other notifications received by BfR,
- ▶ Other BfR findings, e.g. from experimental BfR studies.

- (30) The **quality** and validity of available data, the **degree of uncertainty**, the **variability** of results and unanswered questions during risk assessments should be clearly addressed and described with particular regard for comprehensibility. If recognised guidelines – as listed in Chapter IV, p. 21 et seqq. – are available for an assessment of the empirical evidence, these should be applied. The results of the assessment should be documented. If the information regarding an important aspect of the assessment is scientifically controversial and the scientific findings in this regard have not been compiled systematically, a systematic overview (systematic review) should be prepared and, if applicable, evaluated statistically (meta analysis).

- (31) Certain terms are based on preformed notions because they are defined in legal provisions or introduced as legal terms in industry, law or the public. The concordant use of **legal terms** in BfR Opinions supports the coherence of risk assessments and aids risk management bodies in carrying out their tasks. For legal terms relevant to risk assessment and risk management see Chapter IV, p. 21 et seqq.

II Content and structure of BfR Opinions

- (32) The scientific assessment and other BfR Opinions should contain a **title** and the following main chapters:
- ▶ Subject of the assessment
 - ▶ Results
 - ▶ Rationale
- (33) The structure of the document can be customised to suit the request by adjusting the **subchapters**. The structure can be adjusted individually to suit the subject of the Opinion. Which topics are subject to BfR Opinions are listed in Chapter III, p. 19 et seqq.
- (34) An Opinion is usually sent out as an **annex to a cover letter**. The cover letter may contain information concerning the results, the dissemination to third parties or confidentiality.
- (35) BfR Opinions do not contain the pronouns “I”, “we” or “the authors”, but rather “the Federal Institute for Risk Assessment”.

BfR Health Assessment		 <small>BfR Bundesinstitut für Risikobewertung</small>
Annex		Date
1	Title	
2	Subject of the assessment	
3	Results	
4	Rationale	
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Image of structure

1 Title

- (36) Each document contains a short, informative title. A heading with **key terms** can allow fast classification of the document and contain information regarding e.g. substance, product and matrix.

2 Subject of the assessment

- (37) This chapter serves to introduce the subject of the health assessment. As far as this is necessary for a better understanding, information regarding the **grounds for and background of** the request should be included. If the scope of the question is unclear, it is imperative that this is clarified with the mandating authority as soon as possible.
- (38) Repeating the **request** in regard to prior communication and the status of the procedure facilitates the introduction of the issue. The request should be stated in a manner that allows the proceedings to be logically deduced.
- (39) The **legal provisions** which are the basis for the assessment of the risk and for risk minimisation should be included.
- (40) If a product is assessed, this chapter also includes a summarised **product characterisation**, e.g. by including designation (CAS number, product name, authorisation number or similar), ingredients, format, indications, microorganism, food or the food category etc. Defining and classifying the subject of the assessment is usually necessary.

3 Results

- (41) This chapter should include a short summary and the **conclusions** drawn from scientific research. The depiction typically does not exceed one paragraph. Examples:
- ▶ “BfR agrees to approval of this product/ under the following preconditions”
 - ▶ “As a result of the quantitative exposure assessment, BfR deems it practically impossible that the TDI for X will be exceeded even when high portions of Y (95th percentile) are consumed”
 - ▶ “The health claim made for the food has not been substantiated scientifically”
- (42) The main statement of the assessment (“take home message”) should be unambiguous and depicted in generally understandable terms.

4 Rationale

- (43) This section contains the reasoning that has led to the assessment result. This includes a discussion on whether or not the data used to come to this result are sufficient, e.g. to what extent BfR can follow the claims and conclusions reached by the manufacturer’s authorisation dossier. The typical key aspects of risk assessments (frequency, data basis, etc.) listed in numbers (25) - (29) can be used as a “checklist”. Uncertainties, lack of information and matters of dispute are regularly discussed at the point in the rationale where the issue arises (e.g. doubts concerning the validity of food consumption surveys in the “Exposure” chapter).

4.1 Risk assessment

(44) This subchapter serves to explicate the extent to which health risks arising from a biological, chemical or physical source can be deduced from the state of scientific knowledge and how these should be assessed. It is often sensible to **subcategorise** the response to the request into the following points:

- ▶ Hazard identification,
- ▶ Hazard characterisation,
- ▶ Exposure assessment,
- ▶ Risk characterisation.

However, this should not result in multiple explanations in different sections and can be varied in individual cases if this is justified.

4.1.1 Hazard identification

(45) In this section, the possible risk source (agent) such as a product, a chemical substance (mixture) or a microorganism is characterised. This typically includes:

- ▶ The identification as well as the **chemical, biological or physical characterisation of the agent**; in the case of microorganisms, the characterisation of the pathogen including pathogenicity, virulence factor, minimal infectious dose, tenacity, etc.;
- ▶ Knowledge concerning the qualitative and quantitative **prevalence of the agent** in the environment, in the animal population and/or in the food chain;
- ▶ In the case of microorganisms, pathogen-food combinations and the influence of food technology on the pathogen;
- ▶ A depiction of the occurrence, production and application in accordance with intended and foreseeable use of the agent.

4.1.2 Hazard characterisation

(46) In this section, the hazard potential of the risk source and the pathogenesis with consideration for the agent's intended application (e.g. of the product) are characterised. This includes information regarding possible adverse health effects or other adverse effects, the incidence of disease cases and, if applicable, complications. Opinions on **severity, duration and clinical symptoms** of possible adverse health effects are provided.

(47) Effects/responses are provided relative to the dose. This characterisation should reflect the prevailing order such as:

- ▶ **Toxicokinetics/pharmacokinetics:** absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion;
- ▶ **Toxic effects:** acute toxicity, repeated dose toxicity, genotoxicity, carcinogenicity, reproductive toxicity;
- ▶ **Infectious effects:** pathogenicity, infectivity.

For the **dose-response assessment** of microbial risks, pathogen interaction (under consideration of its minimal infectious dose and its virulence factors) must be described. This includes matrix interaction (e.g. in regard to the growth of the pathogen in a certain food) and human interaction (e.g. in regard to immune status and age).

(48) **Toxicological and epidemiological parameters** should be explained (e.g. NOAEL), and if necessary **limits relevant to human health** should be derived (e.g. ADI, see Chapter IV, p. 21 et seqq).

If in addition to toxicological data, epidemiological or even clinical findings are available, these can be especially relevant for the assessment of risks to human health. The conclusions are to be drawn in regard to all existing sources of information and depend on the quality and methodology in individual cases.

4.1.3 Exposure assessment

- (49) In this section, the exposure of a certain population is estimated. This is based upon:
- ▶ Information on **exposed populations** as well as **different exposure situations** for consumers, users, sick people, pregnant women under consideration of age and body weight;
 - ▶ Information on the **prevalence of the agent**, e.g. which kinds of products release the agent;
 - ▶ Information on **food consumption data** and other information on exposure frequency;
 - ▶ Information on eating habits;
 - ▶ Information on **qualitative and quantitative occurrence** of an agent and/or the residue concentration in and on foods or other products.

4.1.4 Risk characterisation

- (50) Risk characterisation encompasses summarised information regarding the following dimensions:
- ▶ Description of the affected **population** or segment of the population;
 - ▶ The **probability** and if applicable the frequency and duration of adverse events;
 - ▶ The **assessment of type and severity** of adverse health effects;
 - ▶ The **reversibility** of possible adverse health effects;
 - ▶ The **empirical evidence** of a causal relationship;
 - ▶ The type and quality of available data as well as **variability and uncertainties**;
 - ▶ The controllability of the risk.

Consistent terminology should be used for risk characterisation, see p. 8, numbers 24 et seqq.

Frequency of adverse events:

From “often” to “unknown to have occurred”

Severity of an adverse effect:

From “serious” to “mild”

Probability of occurrence:

From “certain” to “practically impossible”

Evidence of risk:

From “generally accepted proof” to “no indications of risk”

Source of data:

e.g. publication, own study

Quality of data:

e.g. systematic review

- (51) In **quantitative risk assessments**, this section is to list and if necessary explain the calculations and mathematical models that were used. In cases where alternative models would have been useful, the effect on the result should be determined as part of the assessment of uncertainty.
- (52) Since natural **variability** in individuals (e.g. biological sex, lifestyle), populations or systems is relatively high, those influences that have the greatest effect on the assessment's result should be identified and explained. The underlying data should therefore be analysed statistically as far as this is possible. Biological relevance should be taken into account as well.
- (53) In order to depict the product risk, it may be necessary to evaluate product-related consumer information. Product distribution conditions, e.g. the marketing of a product to children or for disease prophylaxis could have an essential influence on the risk and the risk assessment.
- (54) **Assumptions** upon which the assessment is based should be documented and explained. Other alternative assumptions that may also be possible are a form of uncertainty and should be documented together with other uncertainties.
- (55) The relevance and influence of perspectives and assumptions on the assessment result should be stated. It is to be stated whether and why **further assessment** or **additional** need for research appears necessary and what information or research is required thus.
- ## 4.2 Other aspects
- (56) This subchapter is optional. It includes additional remarks that go beyond the scope of the risk assessment detailed above if this constitutes a necessary explanation for the result. Such remarks especially concern **misleading** consumer information or further discussion on the extent to which the risk is perceived as a particular threat by the population (risk perception).
- (57) This section may also serve to provide information on **health benefit**, e.g. for the assessment of foods or ingredients that are claimed to have positive effects on health ("health claims") or Opinions on certain diets that are alleged to offer health benefits if the aim is to assess whether or not the claimed health benefit is in reasonable proportion to the risks. However, an exceedance of health-relevant food safety limits cannot be justified by the potential health benefit of a product. This is an essential difference between foods and medicinal products.
- (58) The presumed **effectiveness of governmental control measures** can be discussed if these are connected with the potential emergence of risks or the information has been requested by a risk management authority. In addition, **detection and control methods** can be depicted here, as well as whether the methods that are recommended for official controls ensure success through reasonable efforts.

(59) **Comparative risk assessments** can, as far as they are needed, be carried out here. This may be the case if malnutrition or a lack of vital nutrients threatens the consumer and these must be weighed against other potential risks.

4.3 Risk management options, recommended measures

(60) This section provides information as to what extent **recommendations or options for action** could be derived from the risk assessment that could be incorporated in measures of risk management. If no measures are necessary, this is also briefly noted here.

(61) The following are examples of what may be taken into consideration as **recommendations in the interest of consumer protection**:

- ▶ Restrictions in regard to distribution or professional use;
- ▶ Regulatory limits/standards (e.g. maximum levels in foods when placed on the market, plate count in foods at the time of consumption);
- ▶ Labelling, consumer product information, recommendations and conditions for use;
- ▶ Measures to avoid or reduce entry and/or growth of the pathogen, reduction of the pathogen in the food chain during production and trade (e.g. HACCP, hygiene or control measures) as well as by the consumer;
- ▶ Action against misleading advertising;
- ▶ Increased consumer education.

(62) If BfR provides an Opinion containing recommendations/options for action as a basis for an **administrative decision in procedures regulated by law**, the reference to legal provisions should be as clear as possible. BfR Opinions

together with administrative decisions are subject to review by administrative courts.

(63) In other cases goals, strategies and options for action can be suggested. If several risk reduction measures that appear equally adequate come into consideration, BfR merely provides the responsible authorities with **risk management options**.

(64) If **recommendations for action or dietary recommendations for consumers** are provided, they should be as specific and practical as possible. If different recommendations apply to different sub-groups of the population, definitions and explanations should clearly differentiate between these. If caution is recommended in regard to the consumption or use of a food or product with which most consumers previously did not associate any or low risk, the text should explicitly substantiate why the previous assessment no longer applies and, if need be, why the scientific assessments have changed.

(65) If applicable, the **potential consequences** for the consumer of each measure/option should be stated (e.g. avoiding the risk for the entire population, for careful readers of product labels, etc.). Predictable trends in regard to future distribution of the product in question are stated and taken into consideration for the recommendations.

(66) BfR provides recommendations for consumer protection measures even when state of data is insufficient, if the actual indications are sufficient to cause concern, see p. 5, (4).

5 References

(67) If the text of the Opinion contains a quotation, the source of this is to be provided at the end of the document. Only original quotations should be used. In individual cases it may be appropriate to cite reviews or assessments of expert panels. Citing should be uniform throughout the document and also comply with external standards of citation.

(68) **Example of citation style for the list of references:**

Schellhorn, B., Döring, A., Stieber, J., 1998. Zufuhr an Vitaminen und Mineralstoffen aus Nahrungsergänzungspräparaten in der MONICA-Querschnittstudie 1994/95 der Studienregion Augsburg, Z Ernährungsw. 37, 198-206.

Example of internal citation within the text of the Opinion:

(Schellhorn et al., 1998)

III Scope of the guidance document

The guidance document applies to at least the following BfR Opinions:

Nr.	1. Opinions that are part of law enforcement on the following subjects*	Legal basis in addition to § 2 BfRG (act establishing the Federal Institute for Risk Assessment)
1.1	Food	§§ 54, 68 German food and feed act (LFGB), §§ 50-52 LFGB
1.2	Novel foods	Novel Foods Regulation, Reg (EC) 258/97, Commission Recommendation 97/618/EC
1.3	Genetically modified food and feed	§ 16 German Genetic Engineering Act (GenTG), Reg (EC) 1829/03, Dir 2001/18/EC, EFSA documents
1.4	Maximum residue limits in food of active substances in plant protection products	§§ 54, 68 LFGB, EC Communication drafts, Art. 8, 12 Reg (EC) 396/2005, EFSA documents
1.5	Feed additives	Reg (EC) 1831/2003
1.6	Cosmetics	§§ 54, 68 LFGB
1.7	Plant protection products	§§ 11, 15, 15 b, 15 c, 18 German plant protection act (PflSchG), Art. 36, 37 Reg (EC) 1272/2008, Guidelines for BVL and BfR cooperation
1.8	Active substances in plant protection products, EC active substance review	Dir 91/414/EEC, Annex 1, EC Communication drafts EFSA documents, Art. 36, 37 Reg (EC) 1272/2008, Guidelines for BVL and BfR cooperation
1.9	Plant enhancer/additives	§ 31 a PflSchG
1.10	Biocide products	§§ 12 b, 12 f, 12 g, 12 j German chemicals act (ChemG), Dir 98/08/EC Art. 36, 37 Reg (EC) 1272/2008
1.11	Active substances in biocides, EC active substance review	§ 12 j ChemG, Dir 98/08/EG, Annex 1, 1 a, 1 b JRC documents Art. 36, 37 Reg (EC) 1272/2008
1.12	Insecticide	§ 18 German protection against infection act (IfSG)
1.13	Chemicals	§§ 4-7 ChemG, Title VI, Art. 59, Art. 69, Art. 121-124 Reg (EC) 1907/2006 (REACH) Art. 36, 37 Reg (EC) 1272/2008
1.14	Fertiliser	German Fertiliser Ordinance, German Ordinance on the Establishment of a Scientific Advisory Board on Fertiliser Issues
1.15	Transportation of dangerous goods	§ 7 b Dangerous Goods Transportation Act (GGBefG)
1.16	Reporting cases of poisoning with chemical products	§ 16 e ChemG
1.17	Ballast water	§ 5 German maritime jurisdiction act (SeeaufgG)

* Recipients are usually the Federal Office of Consumer Protection and Food Safety (BVL) or the Federal Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (BAuA).

Nr.	2. Opinions that are part of policy consulting especially on the following subjects*	Legal basis (selection)
2.1	Subjects that are connected with law enforcement through BfR	Bases as stated under 1. above
2.2	Food, feed, foodstuff ingredients, additives, flavouring, contaminants, microbial load, production processes, antibiotics resistance	Art. 14 Reg (EC) 178/2002, §§ 5, 6 LFGB, Dir 88/388/EEC, Reg (EC) 2232/96, Dir 92/117/EEC, Reg (EC) 1881/2006, Reg (EC) 1333/2008, Dir 2003/99/EC, EFSA, CODEX and JECFA documents
2.3	Food health claims	§§ 11, 12 LFGB, Dir 2000/13/EC, Reg (EC) 1924/2006, EFSA documents
2.4	Food contact articles	Reg (EC) 1935/2004, Dir 2002/72/EC, § 30 LFGB
2.5	Other consumer products, e.g. toys, clothing, textiles	CEN standards Dir 88/378/EC and SCHER
2.6	Ingredients in toiletries and decorative cosmetics, odoriferous substances	§ 26 LFGB, German cosmetics directive, Dir 76/768/EEC
2.7	Feed, feed ingredients	§ 17 LFGB, EFSA documents
2.8	Tobacco	preliminary German act on measures to reduce tobacco smoking, German ordinance on tobacco products (Tab-ProdV)
2.9	Governmental control systems, zoonoses monitoring programmes	Reg (EC) 882/2004, Dir 2003/99/EC, CODEX documents
2.10	Pharmacologically active substances	§ 10 LFGB, Reg (EC) 2377/90, Dir 96/22/EEC, Dir 96/23/EEC, CODEX, JECFA documents
2.11	Additional substances, products and noxious substances that are of interest to BfR	BfRG, food law, chemical legislation and legislation on product safety, also for control purposes and in connection with professional norms and standards

* Recipients are usually Federal Ministries

IV Examples of typical risk assessment terminology

The following terms are often used in risk assessments. In BfR Opinions, these should be used as coherently as possible, i.e. in similar contexts, they should be used in the same sense. In order to avoid misunderstanding, it should be noted that on occasion the same term has different meanings in different

disciplines. Life sciences, communication science and legal science do not always speak the same language. For risk managers, the use of legal language influenced by legislation is preferred in difficult cases.

Limits relevant for human health	
ADI	Acceptable Daily Intake (acceptable daily intake of a substance, e.g. a food additive, an active substance in a plant protection product or similar [mg/kg body weight])
AOEL	Acceptable Operator Exposure Level [mg/kg KG/d]
ARfD	Acute Reference Dose [mg/kg KG]
DNEL	Derived No Effect Level (exposure amount derived/calculated from (toxicological) studies and observation data below which there are no adverse effects to human health [mg/kg BW/d])
MID	Minimal Infectious Dose
PTWI	Provisional Tolerable Weekly Intake (provisionally tolerable weekly intake amount of contaminants or residues in foods [mg/kg BW])
TDI	Tolerable Daily Intake (tolerable daily intake of contaminants or residues in foods [mg/kg BW])
TWI	Tolerable Weekly Intake (tolerable weekly intake of contaminants or residues [mg/kg BW])

Epidemiological and statistical parameters	
General: Estimates are stated with a 95 % confidence interval.	
Analytical limit of detection	
Analytical limit of quantification	
Diagnostic sensitivity and specificity	
Limit of quantification	
Incidences	
MOS: Margin of Safety (Ratio of the estimated exposure dose and NOAEL)	
MOE: Margin of Exposure (Ratio of the estimated exposure dose and NOAEL for carcinogenic properties of a substance)	
Odds Ratio	
Prevalence and other frequency measures	
Relative risk	
Risk difference	

Toxicological parameters	
BMD	Benchmark Dose
LO(A)EL	Lowest Observed (Adverse) Effect Level
NO(A)EL	No Observed (Adverse) Effect Level

Microbiological parameters	
CFU	Colony Forming Units
MPN	Most Probable Number
PFU	Plaque Forming Units

Legal terms specified for certain contexts	
“intended use” “foreseeable misuse”	Products: Annex I of Dir 2006/42/EC
“unfit for human consumption”	Food: Art. 14 § 2 b Reg (EC) No 178/2002
“hazard”, “risk”, “risk analysis”	Food: Art. 3 Reg (EC) No 178/2002
“injurious to health” (food) “harmful effects on health” (food) “harmful” (chemical substance)	Food: Art. 14 § 2 b Reg (EC) No 178/2002, chemicals: Art. 2 Dangerous Substances Directive 67/548/EEC
“limit”, “maximum limit”, “threshold value”, “reference point for action”	These terms are used differently in different legal contexts.
“Misleading by claiming effects that are not sufficiently based on generally accepted scientific evidence”	Art. 13 Reg (EC) 1924/2006, § 11 LFGB
dangerous “in accordance with established scientific knowledge”	Chemicals: § 13, 1 German Chemicals Act and defined in EU Commission Case 208/85, § 16
“safe”	Food: Art. 14 § 1 Reg (EC) No 178/2002
“current scientific and technical knowledge”	Plant protection products: Art. 4 § 1 Dir 91/414/EEC
“normal or reasonably foreseeable period of its use”	Consumer products: Art. 5 § 1 Nr. 1 a General Product Safety Directive 2001/95/EC
“a serious direct or indirect risk to human health”	Food: Art. 50 Reg (EC) No 178/2002
<p>“precautionary principle”, “precaution”, “prevention”:</p> <p>These terms are used in different ways. They are sometimes understood to mean that a governmental control measure is inadmissible if it is carried out “only as a precautionary measure” instead of “for health reasons”, if there is no specific legal basis for the precautionary measure. Sometimes “precautionary principle” refers to the circumstance that for a consumer protection measure to apply, it is not always necessary to have irrefutable proof, but only enough factual indications for causality between a presumed risk source and adverse health effects. Measures by the legislative authority that restrict the sale of a product and are not even based on the precautionary principle can be contested according to world trade law. The European legislative basis for the precautionary principle in consumer protection is a Communication of the EU Commission, Commission of the European Communities, Communication of the Commission on the precautionary principle, COM (2000) 1 final, Brussels, 2000.</p>	

V Selection of guidance documents in regard to risk assessment

For risk assessments of BfR, the following documents are especially relevant:

Biocides:

- Webpage: [European Commission – Environment – Biocidal Products](#)
Status: 6.12.2010
- Webpage: [Ex-European Chemicals Bureau: Biocides](#)
Status: 6.12.2010
Contains guidance documents for the assessment of biocides.

Chemicals:

- Webpage: [REACH Navigator – Home](#)
Status: 6.12.2010
Contains guidance documents for the assessment of chemicals.

Chemicals (including residues, contaminants) in foods:

- WHO International Programme on Chemical Safety (IPCS): [Principles for the safety assessment of food additives and contaminants in food \(EHC No. 70, 1987\)](#)
Contains definitions of terms and explains the methodological requirements for the assessment of chemicals (contaminants, residues, etc.) in foods.

EFSA list of guidance documents:

- [Technical report of EFSA prepared by the Secretariat of the Scientific Committee on List of guidance documents, guidelines and working documents developed or in use by EFSA, EFSA Technical Report \(2009\) 294, 1-13](#)
This is to be updated on a regular basis.
- [European Food Safety Authority; Collection and routine analysis of import surveillance data with a view to identification of emerging risks. EFSA Journal 2010; 8 \(3\): \[35 pp.\]](#)
Contains a guidance document on the use of sources in regard to “emerging risks”.
- [European Food Safety Authority; Application of systematic review methodology to food and feed safety assessments to support decision making. EFSA Journal 2010; 8\(6\):1637. \[90 pp.\]](#)
Contains a guidance document on systematic review.

Genetically modified organisms:

- [“Principles for Risk Analysis and Guidelines for Safety Assessment of Foods Derived from Modern Biotechnology” In: Codex alimentarius. Joint FAO/WHO Food Standards Programme. Codex Alimentarius Commission. 2004](#)
Contains definitions of risk analysis terms in regard to GMO.

Microbiology:

- [Principles and Guidelines for the Conduct of Microbiological Risk Assessment, CAC/GL-30, 1999](#)
Contains definitions and explains how risk assessments of microbiological risks are to be carried out.

Plant protection products:

- Webpage: [EUROPA – Plant Health – Plant Protection – Publications](#)
Status 6.12.2010
Contains guidance documents on the assessment of plant protection products.

Review:

- [European Food Safety Authority; Proposal for a Review System for EFSA's Scientific Activities. EFSA Journal \(2007\) 526. \[1-15 pp.\]](#)
Contains an explanation on the methodological procedure when reviewing scientific opinions.

Risk analysis of foods:

- [Codex Alimentarius Commission. Procedural Manual – 19th Edition, 2010. FAO/WHO Food Standards Programme, FAO](#)
Contains definitions of risk analysis terms in regard to food.
- [Application of Risk Analysis to Food Standards Issues, Report of the Joint FAO/WHO Expert Consultation, 1995](#)
Contains definitions of risk analysis/assessment of biological/bacterial hazards and uncertainty/variance.
- [Risk Management and Food Safety, Report of a Joint FAO/WHO Consultation, Food and Nutrition Paper 65, 1997](#)
Defines risk management terms in food safety.

Risk communication:

- [OECD Guidance Document on Risk Communication for Chemical Risk Management, 2002](#)
Contains definitions and recommendations on risk communication in the area of chemical safety.
- [The Application of Risk Communication to Food Standards and Safety Matters. Report of a Joint FAO/WHO Expert Consultation, 1998](#)
Contains definitions and recommendations on risk communication in the area of food safety, especially in regard to the Codex Alimentarius.

Terminology:

- Lewalle, P, Risk Assessment Terminology: Methodological Considerations and Provisional Results. Terminol Standard Harmoniz, 11, 1-28. 1999
- [WHO/IPCS Risk Assessment Terminology, Part 1: IPCS/OECD Key Generic Terms Used in Chemical Hazard/Risk Assessment. Part 2: IPCS Glossary of Key Exposure Assessment Terminology. International Programme on Chemical Safety, 2004](#)
Contains terminology for chemicals (in foods).

Transparency:

- [Guidance of the Scientific Committee on transparency in the scientific aspects of risk assessment carried out by EFSA. Part 2: general principles](#)
[EFSA Journal \(2009\) 1051, 1-22](#)
Contains general requirements regarding the transparency of EFSA risk assessments, i.e. on the structure and content of an assessment or the documentation of the data upon which it is based.

Use of mathematical models:

- [EFSA Panel on Animal Health and Welfare \(AHAW\); Guidance on Good Practice in Conducting Scientific Assessments in Animal Health using Modelling](#)
[EFSA Journal 2009; 7\(12\):1419. \[38 pp.\]](#)
Contains guidelines on the selection of models and integration of mathematical modelling into the answer of a request by way of example in the area of animal health (generally accepted specifications).

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